

THE IMPORTANCE OF ORGANIZING THE COOPERATION BETWEEN TEACHER AND THE STUDENTS IN THE CREDIT-MODULE TRAINING SYSTEM

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Abstract The article describes the main concepts of the credit-module system, its content and essence, which is introduced in the process of reforms of the higher education system of Uzbekistan. In the process of introducing this system, the current problems related to the organization of cooperation between teachers and students and considerations related to their solution are given. The introduction of the credit-module system in higher education institutions was analyzed on the example of data on the topic "Radiodiagnostic equipment".

Key words: Module teaching, credit-module system, radiodiagnostics, radiography, radioscopy, nuclear medicine, independent study.

INTRODUCTION. In recent years, a number of measures have been implemented to reform the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan. For instance, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5847 dated October 8, 2019 "On approval of the concept of the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" mentioned that at least 10 higher education institutions should be included in the list of higher education institutions in the first 1000 places of the rating of internationally recognized organizations (Quacquarelli Symonds World University Rankings, Times Higher Education or Academic Ranking of World Universities) and educational process in higher education institutions should be transferred to the credit-module system step-by step" [1].

Teaching in the "Credit-Module" system has been launched in many higher education institutions, since 2020. In this work, as an example, we will show the priorities of teaching the topic "Radiodiagnostic equipment" through the module system for "Medical Physics" master's education courses.

Analysis of literature on the topic. Renewing education process based on the standards of higher educational institutions means to introduce credit module system in teaching. The credit system is used to indicate the amount of work and time after completing a course or curriculum.

The credit-module system of the education appeared in the late 1960s and was first widely spread in English-speaking countries such as the United States, Great Britain, and Canada. Firstly, this system was used in individual teaching, and later it was considered as a new form of education [2].

The credit-module system is a process of educational organization based on a set of modular educational technologies and credit measures in terms of assessment. Its implementation as a complete system is a multifaceted and complex process. The principle of the credit module system focuses on two main issues:

- organizing students' individual learning;
- assessing students' knowledge based on the rating system.

Research methodology. Cooperation between teachers and students is important in the implementation of the credit module. In modular education, the main roles of pedagogue are to organize, to direct, to guide and to check students' learning process. The emphasis is placed on the independent movement of the student towards the object and the students' individual learning in the educational process. Main importance of implementing this system in educational institutions is improving quality of education, preventing some type of corruption, determining the real knowledge of students to and creating opportunity for the student to study independently and work on themselves. Today, the credit system is widely used in higher educational institutions of many countries.

Analysis and results. When traditional and modular education systems are compared, traditional education is based on the teaching of well-defined subjects and courses to students and the conduct of classes mainly in the classroom. The modular education system is based on educational modules.

The module is part of a curriculum covering several subjects and courses. This is a complex of subjects (courses) aimed at developing students' knowledge, skills and abilities, analytical and logical thinking. In this, the teacher organizes the educational process, conducts live, video and audio lectures, coordinates and monitors the student's activeness. The student should study the subject independently and complete assignments [3, 4].

The credit-module system is a model of the organization of the educational process based on the unit of modular teaching technologies and credits as the units of measurement of the student's educational load. Credit is a unit of measurement of student workload. All types of student work are taken into account in the approved individual plan:

- auditorium (lecture, practical and seminar classes);
- independent work on the analysis of obtained images using modern technologies;
- prepare students to take licensed integration exams;
- passing a practical state exam.

INSTRUCTION PART OF THE MODULE SYSTEM

a) The purpose of the lesson: according to the state educational standards, students should know the following:

- scope of tasks related to nuclear medicine, its physico-technical and physical aspects;
- interactions of ionizing radiation with substances (including biological structures and the human body), protection against radiation and dosimetry issues;

- use of ionizing radiation in medicine, radionuclide imaging methods, modern nuclear medical devices, effects of ionizing radiation and rules of protection against it;
- the main legal documents which regulate the activity of students as specialists in the field of nuclear medicine and radiation safety.

b) Practical lesson plan:

1. Radiodiagnostic methods.
 2. Radiodiagnostic equipment.
- c) Discussion of theoretical questions: 9.25-9.45 (20 min).
- d) Testing: 9:45-10:05.
- e) Plan for independent preparation of students: 14:15-15:00 (45 min).
1. The main specific features of X-rays.
 2. Interaction and absorption of X-rays with substances.
 3. Application of X-rays in medicine.
 4. Computed tomography

Information that the student must know about this lesson:

1. Ionizing radiation.
2. Differences of some types of X-rays.
3. Structure of X-ray tube and small X-ray devices.
4. Priority of computer tomography over X-ray tomography.
5. The effect of X-rays on the human body.

INFORMATION BASED ON PRACTICAL LESSON:

(The text in the module system is shortened).

Radiological examinations are one of the most common methods in modern medicine. For example, X-rays are effectively used to obtain simple X-rays of bones and internal organs, fluorography, computed tomography, angiography, etc. [5].

The effect of radiation on living organisms is not always beneficial. Based on this, X-rays can have a negative effect on human health in a certain dose. The main task of radiological examination is to perform radiation with small doses of radiation that are completely safe for human health.

X-ray examination methods are rarely used in the case of pregnancy and children, but patients of this category should also undergo X-ray examinations if necessary.

Without doubt, some questions are interested to many such as what are X-rays are and how they affect the human body.

X-rays are a type of electromagnetic radiation, other forms of which are light or radio waves. The peculiarity of X-ray radiation is that it has a high-frequency wave, the high frequency allows for a large amount of radiation energy and gives X-rays a high ability to penetrate into matter. Therefore, unlike light rays, X-rays can pass through the human body, which allows imaging of internal structures [6].

X-ray radiation refers to electromagnetic waves with a wavelength of $\lambda \approx 80-10^{-5}$ nm. Long-wave X-rays border on ultraviolet rays, and short-wave X-rays border on UV rays. X-rays are generated in an X-ray tube. A bunch of electrons are released from the heated cathode and get accelerated in the electric field between the cathode and the anode. Electrons with a speed close to the speed of light are braked in the electrostatic field of the anode element and braked X-rays are produced. Anode is made of heat-resistant metal. Its upper part is covered with tungsten and is cooled by a rotating blade. During electron braking, part of its energy goes to generate X-ray photons, and part to heat the anode element. The wavelength of the X-rays produced depends on the voltage of the X-ray tube

$$eU = hv_{\max} = hc/\lambda_{\min}, \lambda_{\min} = \frac{hc}{eU} \quad \text{or}$$

$$\lambda_{\min} = 12,3/U.$$

X-rays are divided into soft and hard X-rays depending on the wavelength.

The X-ray flux is found from the following expression:

$$F = KIU^2Z$$

There I and U are the amperage and voltage between the x-ray tube electrodes. $K=10^{-9} B^{-1}$. Coefficient of proportionality. Z- order number of anode element material [7,8].

If we increase the voltage between the electrodes of the X-ray tube, a linear spectrum appears in the total spectrum, which is called characteristic X-ray radiation. In this case, the electrons start knocking out electrons from the inner layers (K, L, M...) of the atom (anode).

X-rays with an energy of 60-120 KV are used in medicine for the diagnosis of internal organs. The mass coefficient of attenuation is determined using the formula $\mu_M = K\lambda^3 Z^3$. X-rays are used in two ways in diagnosis.

1.Roentgenoscopy - in which the image is observed on a luminescent X-ray screen. In this case, the patient stands between the x-ray source and the fluorescent screen. A fluorescent screen consisting of cesium iodide is illuminated by X-rays and the examined organ forms a shadow of X-ray radiation depending on its density.

2.Roentgenography is a method of recording an X-ray image on photographic film. In this case, the examined organ is placed between the X-ray radiation and the photo film. Bones, muscle tissue breaks, lungs, presence of fluid in the lungs, heart size, shape, etc. are shown with the help of X-rays.

In modern medicine, X-ray tomography or its "machine variant" CT tomography is widely used. In medicine, X-rays are used to destroy malignant tumors for the purpose of treatment. This method is called X-ray therapy in medicine.

X-rays have a harmful effect on biological tissues. Under its influence, wounds are formed on the skin. The following changes occur in the body under the influence of X-rays:

Long-term radiation causes irreversible processes in the composition of the blood - hemolytic anemia.

Change in blood composition.

Leukemia occurs.

It causes rapid aging and rapid death.

It causes genetic changes, creates cataracts.

I. Lecture on the module system

The text of the lecture was given on the topic of "Radiodiagnostic equipment".

Besides:

a) Lecture presentation. b) Presentation of X-ray devices. v) The X-ray computer tomography device is presented.

Level of the students' knowledge:

I. Educational tests.

II. Situational tests.

III. Students will be evaluated through control tests, face to face interviewed (the teacher will ask question and student will answer orally) independent work and activeness during the lesson . [9-12].

Conclusions and suggestions. In short, through the module system, the student can enter the system at any time and learn the information there. They can strengthen their knowledge by working in the module system with the necessary literature, familiarizing with videos on the topic, learning tests on the topic, solving situational tests, and doing controlling tests at the end of the lesson, answering questions orally . It creates convenience in the process of assessing student knowledge, as well as professors have the opportunity to control the activeness of the students on the given topic, the level of their knowledge.

In short, the transition to this system is the demand of this era, all of us should make good use of the achievements of world experience and not repeat its shortcomings. If we take into account successfully implementation of the credit-

module system , students'hard work on this basis, and rise in independent learning in our country , this system expands the worldview of students and helps them to become experts of their fields.

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